

1 **Greb1 functions at multiple developmental transitions.**

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7 We observed Greb1-based switching in multiple developmental transitions: during specification of the
8 CD4+ T cell from the HSC, as well as during specification of the mesoderm from human embryonic stem
9 cells.

10 Citations

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